

Computational studies of emergent autowave
phenomena in capillary tubes

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Abstract

Travelling autowaves are a particular feature of nonlinear active media. Those waves are characteristic of action potential propagation in cardiac and neuronal tissue, while qualitative analogous phenomena can be produced in man-made physico-chemical laboratory experiments, such as the Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction (BZR). The waves can appear in several forms: straight, curved and circular fronts in 2D and pseudo-2D systems, and various smooth, continuous surfaces in 3D. Moreover, spiral and scroll waves rotating around an organising centre can appear in 2D and 3D, respectively. In addition to their rich dynamical features and fascinating patterns, further motivation for studying vortices comes from practical cardiac electro-physiology, where rotating wave segments precursor the onset of fatal ventricular fibrillation. As for studies of cardiac dynamic phenomena, the BZR has been proposed and utilised as a viable experimental and theoretical model system for the heart tissue.

A special case of 3D waveforms is a twisted scroll wave, which is also referred to as a helix wave. Such structures were found in experiments when open-ended capillary tubes filled with gel-catalyst were immersed into BZR reactant solution. Although the geometrical constrains were symmetric, distinctive helicoidal patterns arose spontaneously. The aim in this dissertation is to use computational tools to explore how such complicated patterns are formed under unperturbed conditions. The starting hypothesis is that roughness of the gel-solution interface induces fluctuations which give rise to rotating vortices. Then, the 3D helix is a spatially developed structure of a 2D spiral with a phase shift along the length of the capillary tube.

Vortex nucleation is first studied in a 2D space using a model, which is constructed by adding a phenomenological variable describing the effective spatial excitability into a two-variable Oregonator model of the BZR. The saturation of the initially inactive reactor by reactant diffusion through an uneven interface is modelled by allowing reactant diffusion from random point sources. It is shown that in some parameter values of excitability and the density of point sources at the interface, the diffusion of reactants combined with

oscillatory reaction kinetics can give rise to spiral and phase waves. Then, the same model is extended to 3D space using a rectangular elongated reactor and 3D analogy of the 2D gel-solution roughness model. The calculations demonstrate that a spiral segment can evolve autonomously into a helicoidal wave. It should be stressed that this is strictly an initial-value problem, and the appearance of helices in simulations is stochastic just like in the motivating laboratory experiments. The dynamics of the BZR wave evolution in experiments was investigated further in space-time plane. In the early phase, when the diffusion has saturated the medium only partially, distinctive space-time patterns arise. Some waves penetrate only short distance into the medium, whilst others penetrate much further. Clear transmission patterns, e.g. one 'long' trace after every three 'short' waves was found. Numerical simulations of a five-variable Oregonator model reduced to 1D space with initial and boundary conditions similar to those of the experiments reproduced the experimentally observed findings.

In conclusion, it was shown that symmetry-broken wave forms in 2D as well as in 3D can be triggered by inhomogeneous diffusion of reactants into homogeneous reaction media. Although the media utilised for reaction-diffusion systems are 'numerical', the connection to the corresponding 'wet' laboratory experiments was maintained. Thus the results and argumentation provide more impetus for further theoretical and experimental studies alike.

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1 Introduction

Travelling autowaves of excitation are observed and studied in various spatio-temporal living and non-living media. Such systems are numerous and they span over diverse fields of science. For instance, chemical waves in permanganate oxidation of oxalic acid [1], the aggregation of the *Dictyostelium discoideum* slugs [2], oxidation waves in the Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction (BZR) [3, 4, 5], Ca^{2+} waves in the cytoplasm of *Xenopus laevis* oocytes [6], catalytic CO oxidation on Pt(110) surface [7], sustained proton and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (phosphate) waves in intracellular media [8], vortices in nonlinear optics [9], the spread of influenza [10], and waves of electrical activity in neuronal [11] and cardiac [12, 13] tissue. In general, the waves propagate according to Huygens' principle: no interference and no amplitude damping. The waves fronts can appear in several forms. For instance, straight, curved and circular fronts in 2D and pseudo-2D systems, and various smooth, continuous surfaces in 3D. Moreover, more complex wave forms such as spiral and scroll waves rotating around an organising centre can appear in 2D and 3D, respectively. Those dissipative vortex-like waves have attracted lots of interest due to their rich dynamical features and fascinating patterns that they exhibit. Further motivation for studying vortices comes from practical cardiac electro-physiology, where rotating wave segments precursor the onset of fatal ventricular fibrillation [14, 15]. Recent advances in cardiological functional imaging *in vivo* have given more insight to those theories. For example, magnetocardiography (MCG) using superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) can reconstruct accurate 3D conduction pathways of electrical activity in the heart, as well as re-entries and heterogeneities in the myocardium [16, 17]. As for studies of cardiac dynamic phenomena, the BZR has been proposed and utilised as a viable experimental model system for the excitable heart tissue [18, 19].

However, in many cases the exact origin of spontaneously generated vortices is generally not identified. In the case of isotropic media, one general hypothesis is that dust particles induce local, microscopic perturbations about which organising centres evolve. Particular studies of the BZR have characterised the appearance of spiral waves under special con-

ditions. In an inhomogeneous reaction media comprised of catalyst-loaded beads, it was found that the number of spirals can depend strongly on the bead size (i.e., the characteristic ‘cellular’ structure of the medium) and excitability [20]. Geometrical constraints together with heterogeneous refractory properties can give rise to rotating vortices [21, 22, 23]. In ‘numerical’ excitable media, turbulent spirals are reported in a discrete model showing analogy in cardiac physiology [24], and in a modified FitzHugh–Nagumo model with delayed-inhibitor production [25]. In oscillatory media, a pair of singular points with zero amplitude has been shown to create a non-uniform phase distribution that develops into a spiral wave [26]. Moreover, nonmonotonic inhibition profile in the wave back can induce vortex nucleation when wave fronts collide appropriately [27].

A special case of 3D waves is a twisted scroll wave, which is also referred to as a helicoidal or helix wave [28, 29, 30]. Theoretical work on helices has provided tools for analytical treatment of their dynamics, selection, and stability [28, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35]. However, the theoretical work done so far is subject to idealised isotropic conditions and there is much less experimental quantitative data to relate all those theories to natural phenomena. Yet fewer are reports on spontaneously formed helices in active media. This is a striking contrast to widely and extensively studied 2D spiral waves. From a phenomenological point of view, there is no doubt that helicoidal autowaves, just like 2D spirals, are linked to biophysical processes. So far the best example of such phenomenon is the *Dictyostelium* morphogenesis [36, 37].

In the BZR, helicoidal wave forms can be created from straight scroll waves by using some sort of perturbation (e.g., heat) which induces a gradient of excitability along the rotational axis of the scroll wave [29, 38, 39]. As for autonomously formed helices in unperturbed conditions, such cases are limitedly reported in a certain type of experiments utilising thin capillary tubes and catalyst-immobilised gel [30]. Such experiments are rather straightforward to construct and execute (Fig. 1, ref. [30]). Glass capillary tubes (inner diameter 1.1 ± 0.1 mm, length varying from 5.0 mm to 6.0 mm) were filled with soft-silica gel (10% w/w sodium silicate) having 0.33 mM immobilised ferrioxalate catalyst. The tubes were then immersed into an aqueous solution containing the other components of the

Figure 1: Schematics of the experimental method. Capillary tubes are filled with gel-immobilised catalyst. This cylindrical mini-reactor becomes chemically active after it is immersed into reactant solution and BZR reactants, others than the catalyst, begin diffusing through the both open ends.

BZR (0.33 M bromate, 0.33 M sulfuric acid, 0.33 M malonic acid). This composition of the BZR mixture is such that spontaneous oscillations arise in bulk solution. Experiments were monitored using a microscope (Zeiss IM-35) and a charge-coupled-device video camera (Hamamatsu C2400, frame rate 25 s^{-1}) to measure the transmitted light through the capillary tubes and the video signal was recorded with a time-lapse recorder (Sony EVT 801 CE). Video recordings were digitised with a frame grabber (Data Translation DT 2851, 512×512 pixels, 8 bits per pixel) and post-processing of the data was carried out on a personal computer.

In the initial state, the cylindrical gel within the capillary tube contains only the immobilised BZR catalyst. The other BZR reactants are free to diffuse into the gel through both open ends after immersing the tube into the reactant solution. Even though this capillary

reactor is spatially constrained, oscillatory dynamics and microscopic physico-chemical fluctuations can give rise to distinctive self-organised dissipative structures. Figure 2 shows a snapshot of typical patterns after 25 minutes from the start of the experiment. A vortex-type organising centre, which was nucleated close to the right open end of the capillary in Fig. 2A, emits waves to the medium on its left (wave length ca. 0.5 mm). Because of the absence of competing wave source on the left, a regular wave train is formed throughout the length of the capillary. Similar wave propagation has been reported earlier with an explicit excitability gradient in the medium [37, 38] Figure 2B shows a capillary tube with an organising centre at its both openings. The one on the right is a self-sustaining helix wave. Due to its stability and higher rate of emitting waves, this helix has become the dominant structure in this capillary. Also a point-type pacemaker can nucleate under these conditions, such as one shown in Figure 2C (the left open end). The pacemaker is symmetrically aligned within the tube and nearly planar transverse waves reach the opposite end. Here the diffusion of substrates from the open ends has not been symmetric; the wave length is not the same in all parts of the tube. In Fig. 2D, similar to Fig. 2C, a helix wave has formed autonomously, whose origin is at the left boundary of the gel. Here no organising centres were formed at the right end which facilitated the formation of this regular helix structure. This particular case is similar to what has been reported earlier by Yamaguchi and Müller [30]. This helix had a twist 1.1 mm^{-1} and a lifetime of more than 15 minutes. These helices emerge in probabilistic manner roughly in one out of five experiments [30].

In addition to these patterns in the capillary BZR experiments, also another emergent phenomenon was found. The space-time presentation of the experiment, one presented in Fig. 3 (different experiment from that is shown in Fig. 2), showed distinctive patterns arising in the early phase of the experiment when the diffusion of reactants has saturated the medium only partially. Take the case of the right open end in Fig. 3A. The waves emanate from a pacemaker-type organising centre that is spontaneously formed at the open end and penetrate at least a short distance (ca. 0.5 mm) into the medium toward the left. Some waves, however, penetrate much further up to the length of ca. 1.3 mm at which the medium is sufficiently saturated with the reactants to support wave propagation.

Figure 2: A snapshot of autonomously formed wave patterns in capillary tubes (inner diameter 1.1 ± 0.1 mm) containing soft-silica gel with 0.33 mM ferriin catalyst. This image was captured 25 minutes after immersing the tubes into the reactant solution. White indicates excited state of the catalyst within the tubes. The blob in C is a CO_2 bubble generated by the BZR. (Taken from [40].)

Because of these two distinctive levels of wave propagation lengths, it is referred to as quantised wave penetration. Additionally, this quantised propagation mode displays clear 1:N transmission patterns. For example, 1:5 transmission, shown in Fig. 3A, is defined as one ‘long’ followed by five ‘short’ patterns. At this phase, the waves from the left open end appear irregularly and much less frequently. Clearly the substrate diffusion overcomes the consumption due to reaction and the excitability increases with time. Activity patterns

from the right continue this tendency and activity from the left becomes increasingly regular correlating with long-lived waves from the right yet not showing any of those frequent short-lived waves (Fig. 3B). At the bottom of Fig. 3B one can see an isolated case in this single experiment where oscillation arises from the middle of the capillary. Then, Fig. 3C shows three quantised penetration lengths on the right. Also, one should note that the period between ‘long’ waves is decreasing. Given more time, the regularity starts breaking down on the right: both the transmission and quantisation disappears (Fig. 3D, towards the end of the frame). Yet more complex patterns are exhibited in Figs. 3E–F where one can see traces of secondary activity appearing ca. 0.5 mm from the right end indicating the formation of helicoidal wave form.

The aim of this dissertation is to use numerical tools to explore how the experimentally observed chemical helix and wave transmission phenomena discussed above are formed under unperturbed conditions. The starting hypothesis is that the roughness, i.e. imperfections, in the gel–solution interface induce localised fluctuations which give rise to a rotating vortex. The diffusion of reactants from the open tube ends induces an excitability gradient along the length of the tube. Then, when the vortex penetrates further into the medium, the excitability gradient generates a phase shift along the length of the tube thus driving the formation of a helicoidal wave form. As for the space–time patterns, the dynamics is studied in a reduced spatial model. The reaction–diffusion models that are utilised herein are derived from the Oregonator model of the BZR. Special emphasis is given to design simulations so that they reflect phenomenologically the actual experimental conditions. Moreover, the motivation is to study pattern formation driven by the diffusion of reactants, other than the catalyst and the propagator species, which are usually considered in excess and distributed uniformly in space.

The rest of this dissertation is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the models of the BZR used in numerical simulations throughout this work. Section 3 shows results of diffusion–driven spiral wave formation in 2D media, giving the basis for the ‘roughness’ model of the gel–solution interface in the motivating experiments. Section 4 extends the model used in Section 3 to three spatial dimensions and presents autonomous formation

Figure 3: Space–time representation of diffusion–driven wave patterns in a capillary tube: x–axis, space; y–axis, time; the time increases in the downwards direction. White and black indicate the oxidised (excited) and the reduced (unexcited) state of the ferroin catalyst, respectively. Each space–time frame consists of 256 horizontal data extracted along the centre axis of the capillary at 200 ms intervals (i.e., the span of each frame is six minutes) and each spatial datum is an average of two pixel rows. The tube length is 5.0 mm. (Taken from [40].)

of helix waves. Section 5 represents simulations of reduced spatial model, in which the motivation is to reproduce experimentally observed complicated wave transmission phenomenon. Ideas of related future works, as well as scientific and technical challenges are discussed in Section 6. At the end, conclusions are presented in Section 7.

2 Belousov–Zhabotinsky reaction models

In short, the BZR is the oxidation reaction of malonic acid by bromate which is catalysed by metallo–complexes in an acidic solution. The fundamental work on specifying its mechanism was done by Field, Körös and Noyes (FKN). They presented a rather complex reaction system, which expressed the characteristic dynamics observed earlier in a real chemical environment [41]. Then, Field and Noyes reduced the scheme into a model consisting of three variables, which is referred to as an Oregonator model of the BZR [42]. Perhaps the most widely adopted derivative of the original Oregonator was presented by Tyson, Fife, and Keener [43, 44]. Their approach was based on a model describing the BZR reaction by five chemical substances

where $A = [\text{BrO}_3^-]$; $B = [\text{bromomalonic acid}] + [\text{malonic acid}]$ ($[\text{BrMA}] + [\text{MA}]$); $P = [\text{HOBr}]$ (hypo–bromous acid); $U = [\text{HBrO}_2]$ (bromous acid); $V = [\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ (the catalyst of the reaction); $W = [\text{Br}^-]$; k_i ($i = 1, \dots, 5$) are rate constants; and h is a stoichiometric parameter.

The corresponding rate equations are

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -k_1 [A] [W] - k_3 [A] [U] + k_4 [U]^2, \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d[B]}{dt} = -k_5 [B] [V], \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d[U]}{dt} = k_1 [A] [W] - k_2 [U] [W] + k_3 [A] [U] - 2k_4 [U]^2, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d[V]}{dt} = 2k_3 [A] [U] - k_5 [B] [V], \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d[W]}{dt} = -k_1 [A] [W] - k_2 [U] [W] + h k_5 [B] [V]. \quad (10)$$

As for kinetic parameters, the so called Tyson and Keener’s ‘Lo’ values [44] are $k_1 = 2.0 \times [\text{H}^+]^2 \text{ M}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_2 = 1.0 \times 10^6 [\text{H}^+] \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_3 = 40.0 \times [\text{H}^+] \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_4 = 2.0 \times 10^3$

$M^{-1} s^{-1}$, and $k_5 = 0.4 M^{-1} s^{-1}$. With these parameter values, Eqs. (6)–(10) is a *stiff* set of differential equations.

When A and B are assumed to remain at constant levels in time (i.e., in excess), the law of mass action applied to reactions (1)–(5) yields the following coupled ordinary differential equations:

$$\epsilon \frac{du}{d\tau} = qw - uw + u - u^2, \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dv}{d\tau} = u - v, \quad (12)$$

$$\epsilon' \frac{dw}{d\tau} = -qw - uw + fv, \quad (13)$$

where τ is dimensionless, scaled time. The above set of three equations has been obtained with the following scaling:

$$u = [U] \times \frac{2k_4}{k_3[A]}, \quad (14)$$

$$v = [V] \times \frac{k_4 k_5 [B]}{(k_3 [A])^2}, \quad (15)$$

$$w = [W] \times \frac{k_2}{k_3 [A]}, \quad (16)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{k_5 [B]}{k_3 [A]}, \quad (17)$$

$$\epsilon' = \frac{2k_4 k_5 [B]}{k_2 k_3 [A]}, \quad (18)$$

$$q = \frac{2k_1 k_4}{k_2 k_3}, \quad (19)$$

$$f = 2h. \quad (20)$$

This model can be simplified even further by assuming that w is in quasi-steady state ($dw/d\tau = 0$). Thus, the value of w is given by

$$w = \frac{fv}{u+q}, \quad (21)$$

and the model of three variables, Eqs. (11)–(13), can be reduced to a two-variable model, which has the form

$$\frac{du}{d\tau} = \epsilon^{-1} \left(u - u^2 - fv \frac{u-q}{u+q} \right), \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dv}{d\tau} = u - v. \quad (23)$$

Variable u is usually referred to as *propagator* or *fast variable*, which describes the scaled concentration of HBrO_2 , while the slow *recovery* variable v models the state of the catalyst (e.g. cerium or ferriin) of reaction. In the three-variable version, Eqs. (11)–(13), the variable w describes the *inhibitor* of the reaction.

Equations (22)–(23) describe the state of mean-field (ensemble average) values of the scaled dimensionless variables u and v . In that form, the reaction is assumed to evolve in an ideal continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR). In a more realistic model of distributed chemical system, one has to incorporate the spatial dependency factors by adding terms describing the effect of molecular diffusion. The spatially distributed and unmixed system can be described with the following set of partial differential equations

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = D_u \nabla^2 u + \epsilon^{-1} \left(u - u^2 - f v \frac{u - q}{u + q} \right), \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = D_v \nabla^2 v + u - v, \quad (25)$$

where D_u and D_v are the dimensionless diffusion coefficients of u and v , respectively, and ∇^2 is the Laplacian operator. Depending on the dimensionality of the space of the system of interest, the Laplacian is $\nabla^2 = \partial^2/\partial x^2$ (1D), $\nabla^2 = \partial^2/\partial x^2 + \partial^2/\partial y^2$ (2D), or $\nabla^2 = \partial^2/\partial x^2 + \partial^2/\partial y^2 + \partial^2/\partial z^2$ (3D). Jahnke *et al.* [45] derived values of D_u and D_v from the molecular weights of HBrO_2 and ferriin, and they got $D_v/D_u = \sqrt[3]{113/596} \approx 0.6$. Therefore for the simulations of aqueous ferriin-catalysed BRZ one can set $D_u = 1$ and $D_v = 0.6$.

The space unit su in Eqs. (24)–(25) is

$$su = \sqrt{\frac{D}{k_5 ([\text{MA}] + [\text{BrMA}])}}, \quad (26)$$

where D is the molecular diffusion coefficient, whose value is generally approximated by $1.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [44, 45]. Tyson and Keener used another scaling, in which they set $D_u = D_v = \epsilon$ [44]. In their case, one has to include term $k_3 [\text{BrO}_3^-]$ in the unit of space [45]. The time unit tu is given by

$$tu = \frac{1}{k_5 ([\text{MA}] + [\text{BrMA}])}. \quad (27)$$

One has to remember that the scaling of time and space depends on the reagent concentrations and kinetic parameters.

The two-variable Oregonator, Eqs. (24)–(25) above, is suitable for simulations of a homogeneous BZR. With an immobilised catalyst patterns, such as bathoferroin catalyst printed on a membrane [23], the model can be easily adapted for a modelling of heterogeneous and anisotropic spatial systems. In order to account for the spatial distribution of the other reactants than the propagator and the catalyst, phenomenological approach is taken to extend the two-variable model. The effective excitability has a complicated relation to the relevant BZR reactants, such as BrO_3^- , H^+ , Br^- , HOBr , malonic acid, and other species. This excitability property is then modelled with a dimensionless variable r ,

$$0 \leq r \leq 1. \quad (28)$$

The interpretation of r is straightforward. In the absence of reactants, $r = 0$, the relative excitability is nil. On the other hand, when all reactants are present, the relative excitability equals to unity. Considering that r is de-coupled from the catalyst variable v , the linear coupling of r and the reaction dynamics is modelled by

$$\hat{u} = u r. \quad (29)$$

The resulting three-variable system based on Eqs. (24–25) and (29) is then given by

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \tau} = D_u \nabla^2 u + \epsilon^{-1} \left(\hat{u} - \hat{u}^2 - f v \frac{\hat{u} - q}{\hat{u} + q} \right), \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} = D_v \nabla^2 v + \hat{u} - v, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{\partial r}{\partial \tau} = D_r \nabla^2 r, \quad (32)$$

where ∇^2 is Laplacian operator. Terms ϵ , q , and f are the standard parameters of the Tyson–Fife model, Eqs. (22)–(23), and D_u , D_r , and D_r are linear diffusion coefficients. Parameter f describes the excitability: larger f value translates to less excitable reaction kinetics. If one considers soft-silica (i.e., water-glass) gel, the ratio of the diffusion coefficients D_r/D_u can be set unity. In another gel, like hard mesoporous silica gel (pore diameter ca. 40 Å), the diffusion coefficients depends on the size of hydrated molecule [46, 47]. However, in Eq. (32) it is inclusively set that all the reactants have the same diffusivity. Therefore only the case of equal diffusivities is considered with this model.

3 Spiral formation in two-dimensional media

In this section, computational studies of pattern formation in a spatially distributed BZR model with an emphasis to identify the conditions which lead to spontaneous spiral formation is presented. A 2D reaction medium is considered, which initially contains only the immobilised catalyst. Then, the reaction medium is thought to be in contact with an ideal reservoir containing the other reactants for the BZR in excess: BrO_3^- , H^+ , Br^- , HOBr , malonic acid, and other species. The composition of the reactants is thought to be such that chemical oscillations can arise spontaneously in the presence of catalyst. The lateral diffusion of reactants in the reaction medium is allowed to occur through a set of randomly distributed discrete points. Under the present conditions, the reaction is initiated when the reactants come into contact with the catalyst and the characteristic oscillations begin spontaneously. It will be shown that the spatial coupling of both the diffusion of the reactants and the oscillatory kinetics gives rise to intricate pattern formation including rotating spiral segments and phase waves.

The main idea in the implementation of the diffusion model is that there are two types of diffusion sites on the integration grid. A site is defined as one grid point (area Δ^2 in dimensionless units). Any given site is an *open site*, i.e. it is connected to the reservoir of reactants, with probability p , and a *closed site* with probability $1-p$. This parameter p , in fact, specifies the the *density* of open diffusion sites in the surface. Then, the value of r at the location of open sites is kept in the maximum value $r_{max} = 1$ and constant throughout the simulation. In the initial state, the closed sites are given the value $r_{min} = 0$. For any definite system size with $0 < p \leq 1$ the asymptotic solution of Eqs. (29)–(32) converges to that of the original two-variable Oregonator, Eqs. (24)–(25). Intuitively it is clear that the saturated state is obtained faster with higher probabilities of p . An example and details of a populated grid is shown in Fig. 4.

The kinetic parameters in the model were chosen as a combination of Tyson’s ‘Lo’ and Field–Försterling values: $q = 0.002$ and $\epsilon = 0.05$ [44, 48, 45]. Since the focus is on spontaneous pattern formation, the excitability parameter f was kept in oscillatory do-

Figure 4: Left: randomly populated square grid of 128×128 sites with density $p = 0.1$. Black and white indicate open and closed sites, respectively. Right: detail view of the lattice showing clusters of open sites. Parameter s indicates the cluster size.

main $f \leq 1.60$. Figure 5 shows typical examples of the simulations of Eqs. (30–32). With $p = 0.0100$, the long-term behaviour is characterised by chaotic spiral turbulence (Fig. 5A). However, increase of p to 0.0625 decreases substantially the number of the spiral segments (Fig. 5B). Increasing p further on changes remarkably the qualitative behaviour of the system. Figure 5C shows spontaneous patterns arising from randomly distributed nucleation sites with $p = 0.0750$. At first, several closely packed circular patterns arise, some of which then fuse together and the overall asymptotic behaviour is more like a mixture of stochastic oscillating domains and phase waves. Once p is brought high enough, e.g. $p = 0.1500$, all of the distinguishable patterns disappear and the long-time behaviour is characterised by large, nearly synchronous oscillating domains (Fig. 5D).¹

¹Animations of the time evolution are available at URL <http://www.iki.fi/petterik/sci/pre1999/>

Figure 5: Two–dimensional simulations of pattern formation with varying open diffusion site density p . The grey–scale image shows the dimensionless concentrations of propagator u with white mapped to the highest value and black assigned to the steady–state value. The open diffusion site density p in each case is: $p = 0.0100$ (a); $p = 0.0625$ (b); $p = 0.0750$ (c); and $p = 0.1500$ (d). The finite difference form of Eqs. (30)–(32) was integrated on two–dimensional rectangular grid (periodic boundary conditions) with the forward Euler method using the standard five–point approximation for the Laplacian operator [49]. Parameters: $\epsilon = 0.05$, $q = 0.002$, $f = 1.15$, $D_u = D_r = 1$, $D_v = 0$, grid size 512×512 , grid spacing $\Delta = 1/4$, time step $\delta\tau = 7.8125 \times 10^{-4}$. The snapshots were collected after minimum 10×10^4 iterations. Decreasing the time step by factor of three did not alter the simulated behaviour.

Further simulations carried out to determine the effects of the open site probability and excitability on the pattern formation are summarised in Fig. 6. The phase diagram shows that no characteristic patterns were observed with p above some critical value.

Figure 6: Phase diagram showing the pattern formation as a function of diffusion site probability and f value. Parameters are the same as in Fig. 5, except grid size is 200×200 . Simulations that required more than 15×10^4 iterations to reach 99% saturation level of the reactants were excluded. Symbols: ○, phase waves; ●, spirals; and □, oscillations.

Once considering a condition, $f = 1.55$, the pattern formation with increasing p goes from phase waves to spirals to phase waves and to oscillations. In few cases at low p , phase waves preceded the appearance of spirals. The f value clearly effects the point of transition from one phase to another, although no substantial shifts were observed with these parameters.

Then, the turbulent state characterised with rotating spirals was taken into closer examination. Shown in Fig. 7 is the number of spirals, denoted by N , as a function of density p . It can be clearly seen that there is a specific $p_{N,max}$ where the maximum number of spirals is exhibited. With $f = 1.05$ this value is $p_{N,max} \approx 0.0250$. When f is increased to 1.30, $p_{N,max} \approx 0.0275$, and with $f = 1.60$, $p_{N,max} \approx 0.0300$. The maximum packing of spirals was obtained with the lowest value of $f = 1.05$ investigated. As the f value increases, the maximum packing of spirals appears at higher p .

If one considers that the excitability f is fixed, density p can be used as a control parameter which governs the resulting patterns arising from this model. The spatial distribution of open diffusion sites and the clusters they form play an important role here. However, there are but a few mean-field quantitative parameters that can be extracted from a randomly populated lattice [50]. From a statistical point of view, a reasonable descriptive measure of cluster configurations are the mean cluster size and cluster size distribution. The mean cluster size increases monotonically as a function of p (Fig. 8). As such it does not provide any further clues of phase transition in pattern formation. As for the cluster size distribution (Fig. 9), one can note the following.

- (i) Spirals appear in configurations where the maximum cluster size is ca. 5
- (ii) No patterns are found when the maximum is ca. 25 or more.

Once again, these observations are statistical properties of a randomly populated lattices and can be considered only as a cursory reference for the pattern formation.

Consider that the lattice constant, i.e., the distance between two adjacent neighbour sites, is unity in dimensionless units. More meaningful property in relation to the pattern formation is the distance between neighbour sites, denoted hereafter by ρ , and the average minimum distance between occupied sites, denoted by ρ_{min} (Fig. 10). With increasing occupation probability, the ρ_{min} converges to unity

$$\lim_{p \rightarrow 1} \rho_{min} = 1. \quad (33)$$

Figure 7: Number of spirals N plotted as a function of p . The f value in each case is: $f = 1.05$ (circles, \circ), $f = 1.30$ (triangles, \triangle), and $f = 1.60$ (boxes, \square). Other parameters as in Fig. 5. The N was determined by counting the vortices manually after minimum 10×10^4 iterations.

By combining data from Figs. 6 and 10, the conclusion is that the cut-off for patterns is when ρ_{min} reduces to $\rho_{min} \approx 1.5$. One can relate this cut-off to pattern formation in rather straightforward manner. Diffusion sites packed close enough to each other saturate the medium fast and no patterns arise. As for the distinctive patterns above this cut-off value, one might find clues by analysing the ensemble $\langle \rho \rangle$ and its distribution.

From a phenomenological point of view, the underlying mechanism responsible for the

Figure 8: Average cluster size S as a function of p . Lattice size 512×512 and the data is an average of 50 simulations.

pattern formation in this model can be explained by considering the role of oscillations emitted from isolated clusters of open sites. Figure 11 shows how the phase difference in oscillations can be induced significantly depending on the effective size of a cluster of open diffusion sites. Oscillations begin immediately from an infinite cluster (cluster size $s = \infty$, i.e. homogeneous system) and in this example the period is $T = 4.98 \pm 0.02$ (Fig. 11A). The oscillations in the extreme opposite case of single isolated open site ($s = 1$) start slowly after a quiescent state (Fig. 11B). Once the reactants have spread over the critical nucleation size (for an experimental study, see [51]), the active domain can support full oscillations and the phase difference compared to the homogeneous system becomes approximately $T/3$. The dephasing is very sensitive to the cluster size, which can be seen from the resulting phase difference approximately $T/4$ between $s = 1$ and $s = 9$ (Figs. 11B,C). There are also detectable alterations in the oscillation periods during the

Figure 9: Cluster size distribution for varying p : x-axis, tabulated frequency of cluster size s , y-axis, number of clusters (logarithmic scale).

initial evolution. At very low p , e.g. $p < 0.001$, the clusters of open sites are practically isolated from each other and the coupling length between the clusters is relatively long. Therefore the reaction domains can enlarge without perturbations from other clusters. Therefore only oscillations are observed and no symmetry breaking occurs (data not shown). When the mean cluster size and the cluster perimeter increase, the diffusion from

Figure 10: Average minimum distance ρ_{min} between occupied sites as a function of p .

cluster to its surroundings becomes faster in comparison with the oscillation period. Now the kinetic conditions and the phase of the oscillation can become remarkably different between the geometric centre of the cluster area and the surrounding medium. This is the condition for the dephasing waves to appear [52]. Thus the dephasing of the oscillations in spatial domain and the inherent refractory properties of the BZR give foundation for the evolution of phase waves. Based on these observations, it is reasonable to hypothesise that spirals appear when the deviations in cluster sizes are optimal for generating an ensemble of appropriately dephased oscillating domains. When these domains expand and become spatially coupled, the singularities in the spatial phase distribution [26] and the interaction of the phase wave fronts due to refractory and vulnerable properties in the wave back [53, 54, 55] can form spiral cores. In addition, the differences in the oscillation periods (that can be seen from Fig. 11) enhance the mechanism due to vulnerability. Since the spirals in active media are high-frequency self-sustaining structures, they suppress

Figure 11: Time-traces of oscillating concentrations arising from isolated and symmetrical clusters of open diffusion sites. The cluster sizes are: $s = \infty$ (a); $s = 1$ i.e. single diffusion site (b); $s = 9$ i.e. a cluster of 3×3 sites (c). Kinetic and numerical parameters are as in Fig. 5, except $f = 1.05$.

the competing bulk oscillations and the system becomes dominated by rotating vortices. When diffusion site clusters are large, the system is quickly saturated with reactants. Thus dephasing can not occur in significant degree and no distinctive patterns evolve.

Figure 12: Sketch of the simulated system.

4 Helix wave formation in three-dimensional media

In this section, computational results on autonomous helix wave formation in a 3D BZR are presented. The spatial model of 3D reaction medium resembles a catalyst-immobilised gel in a capillary glass tube (Fig. 12). This model is motivated by real experiments which are described in Section 1 and refs. [30] and [40]. One end of the medium is open to an ideal reservoir of reactants (the other components of BZR except the catalyst) while the other boundaries are non-flux von Neumann type. As the system changes from inactive to active due to reactant diffusion, formation of dynamic spatio-temporal dissipative structures is observed. The results described here contain issues of symmetry-breaking that are not induced by external control. The model employed is derived from nonlinear reaction kinetics with linear diffusion terms.

The reaction-diffusion model is based on the Tyson-Fife scaling of the two-variable Oregonator [42, 43, 44] modified to account for the diffusion of reactants [56]. The three-variable system is given above in Eqs. (30)–(32). The Cartesian coordinate system is set so that the long axis is along z -direction and the boundary connecting to the reactant reservoir is at $z = 0$ (Fig. 12). In order to simulate the initial random diffusion process, which corresponds to the roughness the of gel surface in the laboratory experiments [30], the following 3D boundary conditions are used, which are analogous to the 2D diffusion model

Figure 13: Schematics of the model of open and closed sites at the boundary of reactant reservoir ($z = 0$) and reaction medium ($z > 0$). Panel on the left shows grid (x, y) plane at $z = 0$. Open and closed sites are indicated by black and white squares, respectively. Graph on the right presents how open sites penetrate into the reaction medium along the gray dashed line on the left. In this example illustration $L_x = L_y = L_p = 5$.

shown above in Section 3.

- (i) Any grid site at $z = 0$ is an open site for diffusion with probability p and a closed site with probability $1 - p$.
- (ii) An open site extends into the medium in z -direction a random length (uniform deviate) of maximum L_p grid sites (Fig. 13).
- (iii) Initially the closed sites are set to value $r_{min} = 0$ whereas the open sites are kept constant as $r_{max} = 1$.

After initial simulations it became evident that visualisation of the resulting 3D data presents a problem on its own. Isosurface rendering [57] with appropriate threshold value extracted typically two surfaces close to each other. If the surface is visualised using

Figure 14: Opacity and colour mapping used in volume rendering of 3D voxel data. For example, those parts of the volume with u less than 0.2 are totally transparent but voxels become increasingly opaque as u increases. A standard red-green-blue colour ramp is employed to colour the voxels, again as a linear function of u variable.

opaque graphic primitives (e.g. triangles or tetrahedrons) and only one viewpoint is used, it hinders further the perceived information of 3D wave structure. Therefore a volumetric representation of the simulation data was created by mapping the values of u to opacity and colour (Fig. 14), which is then rendered using ray tracing [58]. This technique does not require any implicit knowledge on characteristics of the BZR excitation waves and produces high-quality visualisations even from relatively coarse grids [59].

Figure 15A shows a snapshot of a selected simulation which exhibited non-trivial pattern formation. In the early stages there is an autonomously formed wave segment, a rotor, rotating counter-clockwise within the diffusion domain open to the reactant reservoir. Because of the limitation of the diffusing amount of reactant at this phase, the excitable medium and consequently the wave is effectively two-dimensional. Given more time for reactant diffusion to enlarge the excitable domain, one can see signs of 3D spatial effects inducing distinctive changes in wave fronts in the less-excitable area (Fig. 15B). The waves emitted by the rotating vortex extend out in space along the long z -axis and become planar waves which propagate away from the rotor. These planar waves disappear when they reach the area which is not yet capable of supporting wave propagation. However, the 3D wave keeps rotating in a stable self-sustaining manner and penetrates deeper into the

medium. Once reactants have reached the other end of the medium (but the system is not yet completely saturated), an intermediate transient state can be characterised. The space ca. 55% in the left is dominated by rotating helicoidal structure and the rest by propagating planar waves (Fig. 15C). This hybrid state evolves then into fully helicoidal structure which extends itself completely throughout the long axis (Figs. 15D,E). The rotor’s rotation time observed from (x, y) plane was $\tau \approx 2.65$ and it remained constant throughout the simulation.²

Figure 16 shows graphs depicting the dynamic evolution of filament shape in 3D space after the helix wave has stabilised completely end-to-end along the long axis. Here the filament is defined as a line-trace along the z -axis of the singular point (i.e., the tip) of 2D spiral of each (x, y) -plane. By denoting $L = L_x = L_y$, dynamics can be summarised with:

- (i) one and half twists and large cylindrical core (radius $\approx L/3$, Figs. 16A,B),
- (ii) one full twist, core radius $\approx L/4$ (Fig. 16C),
- (iii) one and half twists, core radius $\approx L/6$ (Fig. 16D).

Thus, the core radius tended to become smaller with reactant saturation, and the filament to become straight to decrease its length. Eventually the filament broke due to the interaction with boundaries (data not shown) but continuous form was nevertheless re-established. However, this induced additional twist into filament shape and enlarged the core radius (Fig. 16E). Additionally the filament is prominently straight in space 25%–30% on the left during its early development (Figs. 16A,B). This phenomenon has been observed in experiments as well [30].

Results from further simulations carried out to determine the effect of excitability (stoichiometric parameter f) on the formation of singular filaments in the gel-solution boundary are shown in Fig. 17. There is a window in parameter range from $f \approx 1.2$ to $f \approx 1.8$

²Animations of the simulations are available at URL <http://www.iki.fi/petterik/sci/mcm2005/>

within which the rotors are optimally formed and the maximum probability is obtained at $f \approx 1.4$. This suggests that excitability has a modest yet observable relation to the probability with which helix waves can occur. Qualitatively this confirms results obtained in 2D simulations (Section 3, ref. [56]). From a phenomenological point of view, this shows that helices emerge in probabilistic manner, just like in the motivating experiments [30, 40].

These calculations demonstrate that complex dissipative structures can evolve autonomously in a simplistic unperturbed systems. The trigger for formation of rotors (symmetry-broken structures), and of a succeeding train of planar waves, comes from a realistic model of inhomogeneous diffusion of reactants into homogeneous reaction media. It should be stressed that this is strictly an initial-value problem. A study conducted by Steinbock *et al.* found qualitatively similar modes of wave propagation in modelling *Dictyostelium* morphogenesis but they relied on explicitly inducing discontinuities into spatial excitability properties [37]. In this present study, linear diffusion and continuous concentration gradient are key elements in evolution and survival of the helix wave. When the initial rotor emerges, the excitable space is effectively 2D and its expansion in z -direction is slow due to a large concentration gradient of reactants. This provides the rotating wave segment an optimal domain to suppress competing oscillations and to stabilise itself. Once the medium becomes sufficiently saturated and transition from effectively 2D to 3D begins, the rotor has already reached a self-sustaining state. This rotor becomes then the pivot structure from which filament extends itself into 3D space. Interestingly, this type of 2D-3D transition of reaction medium is known to induce changes which may lead to wave breakup and turbulence [55, 60].

Figure 15: Volume renders of variable u using opacity and colour mappings shown in Fig. 14. Data was collected at $\tau = 1667$ (A), $\tau = 2667$ (B), $\tau = 3167$ (C), $\tau = 13000$ (D) and $\tau = 241000$ (E). Eqs. (30)–(32) was integrated on a 3D rectangular grid ($z = 0$, left) with the forward Euler method using the standard seven–point approximation for the 3D Laplacian operator [49]. Parameters: $\epsilon = 0.02$, $q = 0.002$, $f = 1.25$, $D_u = D_r = 1$, $D_v = 0$, grid size $N_x \times N_y \times N_z = 32 \times 32 \times 96$, grid spacing $\Delta = 1/2$, time step $\delta\tau = 3.333 \times 10^{-3}$, $p = 0.13$, $L_p = 13$ (p and L_p were chosen empirically). Decreasing the time step by factor of two did not alter the simulated behaviour. These simulations were carried on a GNU/Linux workstation with 1.3 MHz Intel Celeron CPU and 512 MB of RAM. Effective performance was 41.7 iterations per second in integration and ca. 150 seconds in ray–tracing a single 600×600 image from volumetric data.

Figure 16: 3D visualisations of singular filament with its (x, y) positions projected onto a single plane at $z = 0$. Time in each panel is $\tau = 3333$ (A), $\tau = 8333$ (B), $\tau = 45000$ (C), $\tau = 293000$ (D) and $\tau = 326333$ (E). Filament position was obtained by extracting normalised monochrome image from variable u ($N_x \times N_y$ pixels, one byte per pixel) for each z . These images were subjected to threshold at 200 by mapping pixels below that to 0 (black) and rest to 255 (white). Then Laplacian kernel was calculated to each pixel, omitting the border pixels, with weight 8 to the centre pixel and weights 1 to neighbour and next nearest neighbour pixels. Filament location was in the position where Laplacian field was at minimum. Typical maximum error rate using this method was less than 6%. After visual corrections data was smoothed using five-point moving average.

Figure 17: Probability of rotor formation P (with standard error) in the open boundary as a function of excitability, i.e. kinetic parameter f (Eqs. 30–31) and its fitted curve approximation (dashed line). Model and numerical parameters, except f , are as in Fig. 15. Excitability decreases when f increases. For comparison, the probability of helix formation in the corresponding laboratory experiments was 0.22 [30].

5 Wave transmission phenomenon in one-dimensional media

The complex transmission of waves, which was described in Section 1 and shown in Figs. 3A–D, is an intriguing finding. In order to test an assumption that this is a generic property in nonlinear active media, numerical simulations were carried out by using the five-variable Oregonator model, partial differential form of Eqs. (6)–(10) with diffusion terms added. Kinetic parameters were chosen to model an oscillating medium by setting $[H^+] = 0.36$ M and $h = 0.75$. Major simplification was made by considering a half of the capillary as a quasi-1D system to which reactants diffuse through an open boundary. Since the catalyst is immobilised in gel, one can set $D_V = 0$. Then, the linear diffusion coefficients of $HBrO_2$ and bromide are fixed to unity, $D_U = D_W = 1$ and use relative value $D_A = D_B = 0.5$ (Table 1 in [61]) for BrO_3^- and bromomalonic acid. The initial conditions were $V_0 = 10^{-4}$ M uniformly throughout the medium and the values for others species set to zero, except at the grid point on the left boundary ($x = 0$). In order to simulate open tube end in contact to the BZR reactant solution, the boundary point was kept at constant values of $A_0 = 0.33$ M, $B_0 = 0.32$ M, $U_0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-7}$ M and $W_0 = 3.0 \times 10^{-5}$ M (Dirichlet conditions), and the right boundary is zero-flux (von Neumann conditions).

This model with the initial conditions similar to those of the experiments exhibit wave transmission shown in Fig. 18, which is qualitatively similar to those observed in laboratory experiments (Figs. 3A–D). In the initial state when the reactant saturation is still low, two quantised penetration lengths can be distinguished from the first half of Fig. 18A. By increasing the saturation, the level of propagation length increases stepwise up to four quantised levels (Figs. 18B–D). Thus it is shown that phenomenologically this model reproduces the experimentally observed findings. Detailed view of the concentration profiles, shown in Fig. 19, gives insight of the underlying dynamics. Preceding wave leaves an inhibitory, slowly decaying wake characterised by elevated $[W]$ in regions where reactants $[A]$ and $[B]$ have low profiles. Subsequent wave fronts annihilate upon reaching this inhibitory region. After the value of $[W]$ has receded close to its equilibrium level, the

Figure 18: Space–time plots from numerical 1D simulation exhibiting firing–type wave patterns (axes as in Fig. 3). Elevated levels of variable V are shown as white and shades of gray. Equations (6)–(10) were integrated on a 1D grid using the explicit fourth–order Runge–Kutta method and utilising three–point central–differences approximation for the 1D Laplacian operator $\partial^2/\partial x^2$ [49]. Numerical parameters: grid length, 1024 points; grid spacing, $\Delta = 1/4$; time step (dimensionless), $\delta t = 0.00125$; sampling interval, $500\delta t$; number of samples in each graph, 3333 (2083 time units). The behaviour remained unchanged when the time step was reduced to half.

next inbound wave can propagate through. In the wake of a wave, the rate with which $[W]$ decreases depends on $[A]$ (Eq. 10). Therefore, in regions with low $[A]$, the value of $[W]$ decreases at a low rate. This combined with the diffusion–dependent profiles of $[A]$ and $[B]$ due to boundary conditions, provides the generic mechanism for the evolution of the transmission phenomenon.³

However, there is an artifact in the model which prevents this simulated system from reaching fully saturated state. It appears as an unrealistic jump in the catalyst concen-

³Animations are available at URL <http://www.iki.fi/petterik/sci/chaos2006/>

Figure 19: Normalised concentration profiles $c(x, \tau)$ from the simulation shown in Fig. 18 at $\tau = 8.14 \times 10^3$ (a), $\tau = 8.16 \times 10^3$ (b), $\tau = 8.19 \times 10^3$ (c) and $\tau = 8.21 \times 10^3$ (d). Preceding wave leaves a slowly decaying region of [W] in its wake which causes annihilation of the subsequent wave.

tration in the areas where the waves once propagate but reactants get consumed too fast. The same artifact appears also in the simulations of a closed dimensionless system, which is shown in Fig. 20. Nevertheless, good qualitative agreement was obtained with experiments. It remains as a challenge to develop a reduced model that reproduces the wave transmission phenomenon observed in the experiments.

The quantised length of wave penetration with its associated 1:N ($N = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) transmission phenomenon is to date the first account of such phenomena in experiments of chemical active media. In 2D media, 1:2 transmission is found in a numerical model of CO oxidation on Pt(110) [62] and in non-uniform BZR experiments [63]. Two isolated

Figure 20: Simulation showing an artifact of the FKN model in a closed system. When reactants A and B are depleted, catalyst V increases to unnaturally high.

liquid-phase BZR mixtures with an excitable composition connected with a capillary tube may exhibit resonance patterns up to 1:5 when wave trains are induced electrochemically in one compartment [51]. In the case of 3D media, 1:2 transmission is reported in a study of scroll waves with an excitability gradient parallel to the scroll filament [38]. Yanagita *et al.* discovered similar patterns to ours in simulations of FitzHugh–Nagumo model in which pulses were characterised by an oscillating wake [64]. In their study, successive stimulations of excitable 1D medium, one particular case showed propagation failure in every two waves (1:2 transmission). They also found the train of tracking waves which showed each pulse annihilate but the position of the leading pulse gradually increased with time. Interestingly, Steinbock and co-workers have reported such finding in the 1,4-cyclohexanedione BZR characterised by a non-monotonic inhibition profile in the wake of the pulse [27]. Those two studies [64, 27] further confirm the findings in the present

study that effects in the wake of the waves can give rise to complicated spatiotemporal patterns. The effect of reactants in this matter is undisputed; it is supported by the fact that the transmission patterns could not be reproduced in the model of the three-variable Oregonator derivative with an additional monotonic variable which models the linear coupling of diffusing reactants and the active intermediates, given in Eqs. (30)–(32). Also another three-variable model composed of the activator, the inhibitor, and the reactant HBrO_3 which was employed by Mahara *et al.* [65] in their study of a closed BZR system was tested. That model is not applicable in the present case as numerical artifacts arise when the concentration of HBrO_3 is close to zero. A model that includes at least the three essential substrates BrO_3^- , malonic acid and proton, would be better suited to simulate these observed phenomena with non-trivial initial and boundary conditions.

6 Future works

The process of 2D diffusion-driven spontaneous spiral formation introduced in Section 3 leaves the door open for further investigations. Although a phenomenological argumentation was given based on isolated de-synchronous oscillations arising from separate locations, the detailed microscopic view of the vortex formation remains to be shown. One possible approach is as follows. The spatial model of clusters of diffusion sources is reduced to a case of two symmetric circular clusters: one of an infinite size and one with a relatively small, finite size. See Fig. 21 for a schematic view of such arrangement. The system can be characterised with two parameters. The first parameter is the diameter of the circular finite cluster, denoted by R . The second parameter is the distance from the centre of the finite cluster to the edge of the infinite cluster, denoted by L . By first fixing the kinetic parameters of Eqs. (30)–(32), it should be then a computationally feasible task to carry out simulations with this model and narrow down the spatial parameters with which vortices are formed. Or on the other hand, to find if the model is not complete and requires yet an additional cluster of finite size. In either way, such simulations would give a starting point for further analysis of vortex formation due to spatial phase distribution and refractory properties in the wave back in this model. It would be also a challenge to derive an analytical or semi-analytical solution of vortex formation via interaction in this highly reduced model.

There is yet another possibility to study diffusion-driven pattern formation in 2D. Consider a medium which is saturated by a reactants but in which the catalyst is not initially present. Then, let the catalyst of the reaction diffuse from an ordered or random point sources thus making the medium active. One might expect to see similar pattern formation as it was found in Section 3. This would be an easy from the modelling point of view because the original two-variable Oregonator, Eqs. (22)–(23), would be applicable without any modifications at all. Alternatively, one could use the two-variable Barkley model of excitable media with a diffusion term added to the variable describing the catalyst [66]. Moreover, there would be a viable method or carrying out the corresponding experiments by using an aqueous BZR and vycor-class medium [47]. The diffusion of

Figure 21: Schematics of geometry and spatial parameters of a model of interaction between an infinite and a small cluster of open diffusion sites.

the catalyst could be allowed through porous membrane, perforated film, or carbon nanotube membranes [67]. The use of micro-fabricated carbon nanotube membranes would be highly recommended because of their higher permeability compared to polycarbonate membranes [68]. Both closed and open reactor models could be readily constructed.

The modelling carried out in Section 5 required a model which accounts for the consumption of reactants. The original five-variable reaction system, Eqs. (1)–(5), is a good model for an open reactor which is continuously stirred and fed with fresh reactants. However, in a spatially constrained reactors where spatial properties matter and diffusion of reactants may be restricted or effectively nil, a reasonable model of a closed system is needed. Steinbock and co-workers have derived a three-variable model for simulating 1,4-cyclohexanedione BZR with a non-monotonic inhibition profile in the wave back [27]. Deriving a similar but generalised model for the BZR, or for general active or excitable media, would be academically challenging and beneficial for theoretical studies of large non-isotropic spatio-temporal active systems where non-trivial mass transport plays a role.

There is yet another theoretical and experimental challenge related to the role of hydrodynamic forces in the process which triggers the formation of vortices.⁴ It should be investigated what is the contribution of the physical roughness of the gel versus the gravity-dependent density-driven fingering instability of the reactant solution at the interface. Simple experiments could give a starting point for further analysis. There are numerous examples that spirals can form spontaneously in a quasi-2D hydrogel. Then, if the same experiment is carried out in microgravity conditions, less spirals or none at all would appear if the fingering instability plays a dominant role.

⁴T. Yamaguchi, ‘Symmetry breaks at the gel-solution interface: the growth of 3D helices’, JAXA Chemical Physics WG meeting, 9 March 2004.

7 Conclusion

The autowaves in the BZR is broadly and extensively studied subject in the field on nonlinear chemical dynamics. Consequently, both experimental and theoretical methods and tools of nonlinear dynamical systems have evolved with the research. The researchers have also created imaginative ways to utilise the waves in image processing [69], path finding algorithms [70], and even in chemical ‘clocks’ [71], ‘circuitry’ [72] and ‘computing’ [73, 74, 75]. In particular, the phenomenological connection between cardiac arrhythmia and phase singularities in the BZR has given an impetus to demonstrate every conceivable way to produce spirals and scroll waves. When it then comes to the task of producing spirals, it is almost trivial to design perturbations which give rise to rotating vortices. For instance, one can use light irradiation to control the spatiotemporal excitability in ruthenium–catalysed BZR [55, 69, 76, 77]. Waves have been even made to follow circular trajectories under intelligent control by light [78] – a highly un–natural mode of wave propagation scenario in naturally evolving systems. In this study, external control and perturbations were not considered at all in the formation of symmetry–broken wave forms. Rather, a realistic model of reactant diffusion into reaction medium at an imperfect gel–solution boundary was created. Then, because auto–oscillation is an intrinsic feature of the employed chemical model, it translates to stochastic spatio–temporal nucleations, which trigger cores of spiral waves. The man is left to observe how computer carries out the technical calculation, result of which is a simulated natural phenomenon.

The mechanism for pattern formation, described in Section 3, relies on the diffusion of reactants in active nonlinear reaction environment. It can be associated with several real systems ranging from fundamental physico–chemical models [79] to signal transport phenomena in cell activation [80, 81] to explosive crystallisation in amorphous films [82]. Phenomenologically the model is analogous to a commonplace BZR experiment, in which reaction solutions are poured on a catalyst–loaded gel [46], vycor–glass [47], or synthetic membranes [83]. As the surface of the porous catalyst medium is never ideally homogeneous, it can generate random alterations of diffusion properties in spatial domain. As for the liquid phase, where the first BZR experiments were carried out [3, 4], localised and

random hydrodynamic forces can account for the generation of singularities in the spatial phase distribution thus giving rise to spontaneous spiral waves. Similarly to this model, Steinbock *et al.* made experiments with a BZR in which the catalyst was immobilised onto a polysulphone membrane by printing it in a predetermined dot density pattern [23]. They found that under oscillatory reaction conditions, spiral organising centres are formed spontaneously in an intermediate dot density values. Although the patterns on a membrane are static, it resembles the open diffusion source model presented in this study. Also the results were similar because the ‘density’ was a control parameter for the nucleation of spirals.⁵

The simulations on helix–filament formation (Section 4), verify theoretical predictions by Panfilov *et al.* [28] and findings in real chemical [30] and biological [36, 37] media. The results also provide a further argument that the formation of spiral–type vortices does not necessarily require macroscopic perturbations of control parameters in active media. Rather, alterations in spatial diffusive properties at microscopic level can induce phase shift of oscillating ensembles. Consequently, this can lead to spiral formation in 2D (Section 3) or helix waves in 3D as is shown here. Relevant analogical counterpart to the 3D BZR in biology is neuronal [11] or cardiac tissue [12, 13]. Following the present results, diffusion properties of active species or reactants in such systems can initiate onset of disturbing anomalies even though reaction media as such is capable of conducting normal metabolism.

The highly complicated space–time patterns in capillary tube experiments (Section 5, Fig. 3), may appear at the first sight intriguing but laborious to explain conclusively. To the best knowledge of published literature to date, it is the first account of such phenomena in experiments of chemical active media. However, that phenomenon turned out to be a generic property which can be qualitatively reproduced by simulations of the five–variable Oregonator model with trivial initial and boundary conditions similar to those employed in the experiments. Moreover, the emergence of those transmission patterns could be explained by wave front interaction with slowly recovering wave back

⁵Online material is at URL <http://www.aaas.org/science/steinbock.htm>

of a preceding wave. A model which includes variables for the ‘excess’ reactants and their consumption was required to successfully simulate the transmission phenomenon. However, the modelling of the experimentally observed autonomous helix formation in connection with the wave transmission phenomenon would require yet another approach and computationally feasible reaction–diffusion model accounting for the consumption of reactants. Some further study with such an advanced model might perhaps consider dynamically changing inhomogeneities of the medium, e.g. CO₂ bubbles, as a viable trigger for the generation of helices.

In conclusion, this dissertation summarises three computational studies, each of which shows how highly organised dissipative structures emerge in unperturbed, far from equilibrium conditions. Moreover, each case can be treated as initial and boundary value problem. Although the media utilised here for reaction–diffusion systems are ‘numerical’, the connection to the corresponding ‘wet’ laboratory experiments is maintained. Thus the results and argumentation provide more impetus for further theoretical and experimental studies alike.

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